

The role of speech style between teacher and student in learning English

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the role of speech style between teachers and students in learning English. This study was ex post facto research, using quantitative approach. The students at English Department of Madura University, Indonesia were the population in this research. A sample was decided using proportional stratified random sampling technique. The data were analyzed by simple regression technique. The result of the study showed that the role of speech style between the teachers and the students in learning English is 0.62 (62%). The speech styles of the teachers and students work on students' proficiency level in English. Conducive classroom in language learning is the requirement of the right speech styles of the teachers and the students. It makes necessary for the teachers to provide students with suitable speech style with the contexts in order to put up the classroom serving the students with substantial input.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Every classroom has its own characteristics. The characters of teachers and students influence the run of teaching learning process [1]. In addition, social environment takes parts in arranging the classrooms. Some teachers are not giving the changes to the students to give question, comments and opinions, while others prefer to let them interact by themselves. Some of them are taking their power in authority, while others are flexible in giving the lesson to the students. Sometimes, it is not hard for them to give their smile to the students and to be enthusiastic and patient to look for new ways to get the success in their teaching and help the students to have proficiency level in English.

Teachers' languages are the tools for enhancing students' input in English and creating their comprehension in English [2]. The teachers can invite the students to communicate as participants of English learning. It is important for the teachers to understand their objectives and design the best method to conduct their teaching [3]. They are also able to facilitate the students to interact with their peers as models to get comprehensible input in English. Moreover, they have impacts on personal and behavior of students in language.

It is important for the teachers to design meaningful environment language learning. The teachers will have their own style to do it. Style of teaching is not public way to start the relation with the students and to manage classroom. It is considering the arrangement of behaviors and attitudes characterizing of the teachers in teaching learning process. The teachers should have an action plan defining the interaction of specific choice between the teachers and the students so as to build up specific goals. The goals of teaching are to organize learning situation and to increase the opportunities to communicate in English.

Communication strategies are helpful in assisting students to handle with verbal communication problems [4]. The teachers with good quality in speech style make possible students who have difficulties in learning English to motivate and to teach the students appropriately to their needs. Moreover, the speech style of the teachers is as a systematic technique to convey messages and it can assist students in improving their communication in the target language [5].

Style is language dimension where individual have his own words to speak with others [6]. It is impossible that teachers and students will use the same words to explore their feeling, comments, and opinions. Situation considers the use of teachers and students in the use of words in interaction and communication. Style is the ways of teaching, learning, and communicates with others. There are five types of language styles: frozen style, formal style, consultative style, casual style, and intimate style [7].

Speech style is referring to different degree of language to signal, make up, and introduce varieties of language of the speakers. Speech style affect on the perceptions as well as the communication of the speakers. It is considering the status, social background, education level, of the speakers and listeners. Speech style is the way to express thought through language to show the mentality and personality of the speaker [8]. Speech style makes possible to value the personality, behavior, and ability of the speaker. More fortune the speech styles of the speaker, more fortunate the estimation of people to him or her and vice versa. Speech style has often been approached as a matter of statistical frequency of elements already given in linguistic description or as derivation from some norms given by such description [9]. Speech style also depends upon qualitative judgments of appropriateness, and must be described in terms of selections that apply globally to a discourse. Speech style uses all the resources of language: tone of voice, different ways of pronouncing sounds, even choice of words and grammar themselves [10]. People can identify the speech style of others from the tone of their voice, their pronunciation of the sounds, their choice of words and the grammar. People who are in a formal situation will have different resources of language from those in a non-formal one.

The first, frozen speech style, is called so because the form has never been changing from time to time, from generation to generation even though it has different speaker, for example the style used in Qur'an, Bible, magic formula, and speech. The speaker of this style speaks monotonously and he or she almost does not know the attendance of his or her addressee [11]. There is no reaction from the listener that makes the speaker change his speech style. The second is formal speech style, which is a standard one. It is usually used by a speaker who is in formal situation such as in academy, court, and government speech. The speaker of this speech style will use vocabularies that will not confuse the listener. Formal speech style does not only focus on the organization of vocabularies, but also on other aspects of language such as tone and structure. However, the most important aspect is the choice of words. This speech style is usually used by the speaker to show the distance between the speaker and the listener. In formal speech style, the speaker prepares the cohesive statement stably. This speech style avoids repetitions, slang, and statements or utterances that are only understood by a group of people.

The third is consultative speech style. Consultative speech style is also called semi-formal, because it is conditioned between formal and informal speech styles. A consultative speech style is usually used by a businessman, industrialist and people in small discussion where the addressees are involved in it and the conversation is oriented toward result or production [12]. The speaker conveys the information, including that about his or her background extensively until the listener is sure about it. Using consultative speech style, the speaker does not need to prepare about what will be discussed or uttered. Because of this, the speaker usually makes mistakes in her or his conversation such as by repeating unnecessary words or mistakes in choosing the words. The fourth is casual speech styles, which is also called informal or relax speech style. The choice of words and the sentences used in casual speech style are simpler than in formal speech style. However, human beings may not make a conclusion that formal speech style is better than casual speech style or vice versa [13]. The characteristics of casual speech style are the repetition of a certain word or technical term and the use of elliptic sentences. It is clear that the determiner and auxiliary verbs that are not really important to convey the message are omitted. Elliptic sentences are not common in frozen, formal, and consultative styles. The fifth is intimate speech style. This speech style is called intimate because it is usually used by people who are very intimate, such as husband and wife. The characteristics of intimate speech style are close to the characteristics of casual or relax speech style. Intimate speech style uses private characteristic codes, for example Coffee's cold, which is only uttered as cold.

Speech styles bring their own characteristics in using words. Different situation invite different style in speech. In teaching learning process it is important to the teachers to consider their speech style in order to facilitate the students with meaningful input and getting easier understanding. Pangesti and Prihatini in their study about tip of the tongue' in the utterances of Indonesian foreign speakers assert that teacher must find the easiest speech style to speak with them in order to make them understand in English [14]. Appropriate speech styles given by the teachers facilitates effective teaching learning process coming true and happen [15]. Amiruddin and Tafriyanto in their study about teacher-student closeness state that teachers' behavior

including their speech style such as the ways to give questions, to invite students responds serving the students to have meaningful input as well as to overcome from their anxiety to have interaction in English [16].

Teachers' speech style are important to help students to get success in the target language in particular students with cognitive disabilities [17]. Speech style of the teachers is able to assist students overcoming from their developmental and learning problems. Students who have problems in their English learning or have some difficulties in producing English both in spoken or in written need personality contacts with special speech style to pick up their enthusiasm and to give them out of the ordinary instruction services.

To give good services in education specially in learning English, the teachers of English Department of Madura University have different speech styles. Their speech styles are associated to their personality, background, culture as well. Teachers and students of English department of Madura University come from different culture and background of family as well as social status. Their background are influencing on their style in teaching learning process. They are from urban and rural of Madura as well as they are from Java and other regions of East Java. They are bringing their own culture, habits, in addition to the ways to communicate to their addresses. Teachers of English department at Madura University communicate to the students using different speech style. Some of them use formal speech style whenever they are. Both in formal and informal situation they use formal speech style and keep the distance to the students. In addition, another interacts to their students by using speech style appropriate to the contexts; they are using formal style and informal situation, for informal style they use informal situation. They use style based on the needs of situation. It is important to discuss more about the role of speech style between teachers and students in learning English at English department of Madura University.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The study was quantitative research employed ex post facto approach. This research looked carefully at potential preceding state of the role of speech style between teachers and students in learning English that come into existence and cannot be controlled and manipulated. Questions both in questioners and tests by using interview given to the respondent focus on the ways teachers conducting teaching process, interacting to the students, giving questions to the students, inviting the students' opinion, using appropriate style. In addition, they also have to do to the ways students giving responses suitably to the teachers. The questions are also discussing about the effect on their style in learning English. Moreover, items in the question are about the influence of social factors of English Department at Madura University on their speech style.

The participants of the study were students and the teachers of English Department at Madura University. They are consisting of students who are in third, fifth, and seventh semesters. There were 13 students are from third semester, 11 students are from fifth semester, 10 students are from seventh semester, and 10 teachers of English department. They are chosen as the subjects in this study. Proportional stratified random sampling is used as sampling technique since students of English Department at Madura University consist of four groups. The subgroups' quantity of students is in proportion. The size of each group is in the same rate. They have equal numbers of participants of each group. There were 44 students of English Department at Madura University selected as the subjects of the study. Questioners and the tests by using interview are given to them to examine the amount of their speech style to their proficiency level in English.

Questioners and tests by using interview were employed to collect the main data, while observations and documentations used for supporting data. This research used the questioners to get information about speech style between teachers and students. The response of students was measured in Likert scale. Moreover, the tests by using interview are to measure students' proficiency levels in English including their fluency, accuracy, accent, vocabulary, and grammatical constructions. The observation and documentation are to find out and capture facts of students' activities related to their speech style in teaching learning process. A simple regression technique by a computer program SPSS version 16 for Windows is used analyzed the data. Undertaking simple regression, normality and linearity tests are undertaken. It summarizes and studies the amount relationship between two continuous variables. It concerns the study of only one predictor variable. It studies the amount of speech style between teachers and students in learning English.

This study explored the consistency of a previous experience and the relationship between it and other dependent variables. In cases in which it is unethical to influence or manipulate a depending variable, we tested the hypotheses about cause and action instead of an experiment. There were independent variable(s) in the quest whereby a dependent variable(s) or variables have been observed. Then, retrospectively explores the independent variable(s) and its potential relation to the dependent variable or variables and their effects

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The questionnaires used to get the data of speech styles between the teachers and students at English Department of Madura University. The teachers and students gave responses to the provided questions in the questioners. The statistical descriptive results showed that the mean is 47.45, median is 4.72, and standard deviation is 6.89. Based on the criteria of categories, the speech styles between the teachers and students of English Department at Madura University are formal, consultative, and casual speech style. They did not use frozen and intimate speech style.

The outputs of SPSS program 16 for windows estimation point out that the teachers and the students of English Department at Madura University formal, consultative, and casual speech style. The teachers use formal style to the students when they are in formal situation such in the classroom interaction. The interactions in the classroom invite both the teachers and the students considering the organization of vocabularies and choice of words. This kind of speech style is allowing for the distance between the teachers and the students. The teachers and the students prepare the consistent account steadily. They avoid repetition, slang, statements or utterances that only the groups of people only understand it. The teachers and the students of English Department of Madura University also use the consultative speech style when they are in small discussion to get the results of the topics being discussed. They have no preparation in their sentences; it is possible for them to have repetitions as well as mistakes in their sentences. Moreover, they use casual speech style. They use this style when they are in informal or relax situation. They simplify their utterances. The characteristics of this style are that the choice of words and sentences used by the teachers and the students are simpler than in formal speech style. They are common to have repetition of a certain words and elliptic sentences.

Using English spoken test by using interviews is to get the data of the proficiency level of students' learning in English. The statistical descriptive results show that the mean is 47.97, median is 4.86, and standard deviation is 1.06. The output of SPSS program 16 for windows estimation shows that students of English Department at Madura University are able to stick together the habitual social communication and incomplete occupation requirements. They can hold dialogue of current dealings, occupation, as well as relations; they use vocabularies, choice of words, and utterances in view of situation and the distance between the students and the listeners or addresses.

Test of normality used to determine whether the data in normal distribution. The distribution of sample is normal if the test is non-significant ($P > .05$) but if the test is significant ($P < .05$) it indicates that the distribution of sample is non-normal. Table 1 indicates the result of normality test of this study. Linearity test is linier if the ($P > .05$), but it is not linear if ($P < .05$). Table 2 reveals the summary of linearity test.

Table 1. The result of normality test

		ST	EL
N	44	44	
Normal parametersa	Mean	47.4545	47.9705
	Std. Deviation	6.89271	1.06366E1
Most extreme differences	Absolute	.082	.182
	Positive	.082	.182
	Negative	-.061	-.128
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	.543	1.206	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.930	.109	

Table 2. The summary of linearity test

Variable linearity	Probability (p)	Criteria	Explanation
X-Y	0.11	0.05	Linier

There is a positive and significant role of speech style between the teachers and the students (X) in English Learning (Y) of English Department at Madura University. Table 3 presents the output of linier/simple regression of the hypothesis. Table 3 indicates that sig. (p) is significant. So, linier/simple regression proposes approximation the role of speech style between the teachers and the students (X) in English learning (Y) at English Department of Madura University. Therefore, the role of speech style between the teachers and the students at English department of Madura University (X) in learning English (Y) is positive and significant. The estimation of the independent variable is determined by looking at coefficients' variable as in Table 4.

Table 3. Summary of variance analysis of linier regression

	Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	299.256	1	299.256	2.753	.105 ^a
	Residual	4565.615	42	108.705		
	Total	4864.872	43			

Table 4. The coefficients' summary of the role of speech style in English

Model		Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	29.808	11.059		2.695	.010
	ST	.383	.231	.248	1.659	.105

In unstandardized coefficient of Table 4 expresses that constant $b_0 = 29.808$ and $b_1 = 0.383$. Therefore, regression model that is proposed can be formulated (1).

$$\hat{Y} = 29.808 + 0.383X \quad (1)$$

As a consequence, the model anticipated is significant, the estimation, prediction, and inferential process can refer to the model. Table 5 shows adjusted R^2 score point out that the amount of the estimation is showed in R^2 score. The R^2 score is corrected for part of (b_0) in order to get adjusted R^2 score. The score shows the variant of speech style between the teachers and the students in English learning at English Department of Madura University, but the rest 61% (100%-39%) relate to another factor.

Table 5. The coefficients' determination of speech style in English learning

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. error of the estimate
1	.248a	.062	.039	10.42618

Statistical descriptive analysis in speech styles asserts that students in English learning describing about uneasiness and worry. Students are not really positive of their quality to speak English in group of people. Hesitation, mistakes, and feeling errors of grammar in producing English are their problems. In addition, they have many pauses and sometimes lose their vocabulary and ideas in the middle of communication and presentation. They are not relaxed in test.

Moreover, in English proficiency level, statistical descriptive analysis indicates that students are able to communicate usual public demands and partial profession rations. They share their opinion, ideas, and comments to their teachers and peers with speech style based on the situation. They invite formal speech style in formal situation, but they use casual speech style in outside the classroom.

Speech styles used by the teachers consider the success in teaching learning process. The goals in teaching learning process ask the teachers to use different speech style. Teachers use English speech style appropriate to the situation. The speech style choices can be an alternative for the teachers to make the classroom conducive, to make the students enjoy the learning, and to overcome their stress. Presenting different speech styles in teaching learning process used by the teachers is to create comfortable atmosphere as well as to provide input for the students [18]. The teachers' speech styles can be an accomplishment arrangement defining the relations between the teachers and students to increase goals related to the subjects and behaviors. Moreover, the teachers modify their speech style to understand students' difficulties in learning English. Teacher speech styles are important for the students having problems in learning. Students who have problems with their learning need a special education service including the speech styles used by the teachers.

Speech styles invite the teachers and students to make interaction in English. It is difficult for the students to have interaction in English when the teachers invite students to have questions or to have a discussion in inappropriate speech style. Suitable speech styles used by the teachers build the closeness between the teachers and students. Teacher-student closeness increases the students' motivation as well as decreases the students' anxiety level in learning English. Therefore, students are having high motivation and low anxiety level in learning English when the teachers service them in appropriate speech style. Moreover, Amiruddin [19] in his study about the role of social distance between teachers and students in English proficiency states that there is a positive and significant role of social distance in English. It builds the students proficiency level in English. It is hard for the students to have easy understanding when the teachers of English department show their authority. They have problems and difficulties to acculturate to the

authority teachers since they have distance both physically and psychologically to their students. They have rarely smiled to their students as well as their speech style keep the distance to their students both in classroom and outside the classroom.

Students' speech styles are considering the run and the smooth of the interaction and discussion with their friends and their teachers. Their speech styles choices contribute to their learning. They use different speech styles by considering their distance to their addressee. It is also happened to the teachers in communication. To design effective learning, they select appropriate and the best speech style to make the students in desire to learn and communicate in English. It is relevant to the Winanta *et al.* in their study [20] reported that in filtering the appropriate speech style, the teachers and the students should be aware to the formality and intimacy aspects.

The teachers' speech styles are the main sources in language learning. They bring some benefit in the advanced of language learning, but they create the problems as well in language learning. The style used by the teachers is the major factor of building useless classroom atmosphere [21]. Appropriate speech style used by the teachers facilitates students to have meaningful input in English since it can create conducive atmosphere in the classroom. Large amount of input provided by the teachers are given to the students when they use proper speech style in language learning. Therefore, it is important for the teachers to be aware of the context and condition in the classroom as well as the students' emotional state in order to regulate the speech style.

The teacher-talk and foreigner talk used by the teachers in language instruction help the students to get easier understanding. They simplify their utterances when the students have some problems to get the meaning or they face complicated ideas to generate. Moreover, the teachers are paying more attention to use or to change their speech style based on the context. Discussing the using of casual style in English language Teaching reports that the simplification of teachers' utterances helps the students to have no problem in getting the meaning. In addition, it can enrich the students' vocabularies.

Speech styles of the teachers and students are important in language learning. The speech styles used by the teachers are able to bring students involving the process of learning. The students can learn autonomously and creatively. The teachers give the students to carry out classroom presentations. They put the students into group and distribute topics. Then the students discuss the topics and invite the floor for the discussion as well as the teachers give feedback to the students. The speech styles proposed by the teachers are a way to create student centered learning. It is appropriate speech style can convey message and assist students in improving their proficiency level in the target language.

The teachers are a leader for their students. They take a control to their students' learning. Making conducive classroom is the duty of the teachers. The teachers should provide students with appropriate speech style to manage and support them with meaningful input. It is also important to provoke students' commitment in learning. When the teachers have leadership in managing and controlling the classroom by using their speech style, the students will have a good commitment as well in learning, and it can motivate them to communicate in English. It is in line to the statement of Pramudjono [22] that people with a good leadership is possible to improve others' commitment. Therefore, it is easy for the students to have meaningful input when they are willing in learning English.

Creating effective teaching learning process by inviting students to have interaction in English is a way of the teachers to have closeness to the students. The teachers change their speech style based on the state of environment of English Department of Madura University. The teachers' choices of words are considering the needed and social background of students. The speech styles of people have relation to their ethnicity and status relations [23]. Students are in variants of social class and social economics. Their backgrounds influence on their accents, choice of words, grammatical construction, in learning English. It makes the teachers taking in account to formulate their speech style to design interesting teaching learning process. It is important for the teachers to have capability such as speech style in teaching based on the characteristics of learning obstacles; therefore, the teachers' speech style can be a solution to create effective learning in particular for students who have obstacles in learning [24].

Moreover, each speech style is diverse one another depending on the teachers' communicative purposes. Speech style seeks to change the speaker's communication culture so that it is easier to comprehend [25]. Since much of the utterances are common to students, they will use them in their everyday lives. Teachers' speech style increased speaking motivation would have a positive impact on the learning environment and students' desire in language learning. Appropriate speech styles proposed by the teachers are tools to develop their students' language proficiency [26]. Communication based on the sense of culture often leads to arousing their motivation to speak. One of the linguistic differences, speech style, leads to growing students' desire to engage more effectively in class. To develop the language competence in English, the teachers are expected to use proper language style [27]. The teachers gave a lot of knowledge about themselves just by the words, the grammar, and the pronunciation they chose, both unconsciously and

consciously [28]. This knowledge shows things to the students. Design markers of a specific kind social category or area may be used purposely for other reasons [29]. It means that the teachers use voice style has to decide the intent of contact in language learning [30].

4. CONCLUSION

This research found that the role of speech style between the teachers and the students of English department at Madura University in learning English is positive and significant, and the amount of the role of the variable is 0.62 (62%). The speech styles of the teachers and students manipulate on students' proficiency level in English. Appropriate speech style used by the teachers in language learning help the classroom providing students with input. The classroom is facilitating students input in language learning when the teachers propose the classroom with comprehensible and interesting input. It implies that the teachers should use appropriate speech style in order to construct the right conditions of classroom to help students with meaningful input. The members of academic society should be responsive to proper speech style in English teaching learning process.

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